

Comparing the Approaches of International Political Economy Macro Strategy of the United States of America and China Towards the Islamic Republic of Iran

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ABSTRACT:

US-China relations are the most important and at the same time the most complicated relations in Asia. Due to the rapid growth of China and the efforts of the United States of America to maintain its power in the region, the two countries are in an increasing struggle to gain more power and influence in Asia and experience different levels of interaction and competition against each other. The main purpose of this research is to compare the macro strategy approaches of the international political economy of the United States of America and China towards the Islamic Republic of Iran. The research hypothesis was that Washington is worried about the unpredictable consequences of competition with China, which may lead to a military conflict between the two countries; It has tried to put a range of containment strategies (positive to negative) in accordance with this country's assessment of the impact of China's rise on American hegemony, in order to restrain China and avoid direct confrontation with this country. The findings of the research showed that the United States has used a variety of strategies in an intelligent manner in dealing with its competitors in accordance with the geopolitical conditions of the region and the international public space. The United States of America as the only remaining great power from the era after the Second World War and the Cold War; It has always tried to establish its hegemony in the world and force others to submit and accept its desired order. Therefore, economic growth and development and control of the world's energy resources, especially the resources available in the Persian Gulf region, are considered essential for the stabilization and maintenance of this country's hegemony in the world. On the other hand, considering that this arena can be such that in case of insecurity in this region, the hegemony of this country will be challenged. Therefore, for several decades, this country has focused its strategy on reducing dependence on energy imports. China is also one of the great powers that is trying to improve its position in the world arena, and this in turn determines the country's dependence on the energy resources of the Persian Gulf. Thus, what is important for China is the security of energy supply.

Keywords: *Macro strategy of political economy, international politics, United States of America, China, Iran.*

INTRODUCTION:

The emergence of different concepts, theories, and fields of study in the field of political science is influenced by the occurrence of special developments and conditions that lead to appropriate reflection and analysis. International political economy, as claimed by most mainstream theorists, is basically a sub-branch of international relations knowledge that emerged and evolved as a result of some developments in the realities of international relations during the decades after the World War II (Guo et al., 2021; Segura-Ubierno et al., 2007).

This approach is in contrast to another approach that considers international political economy as a branch of classical political economy. Referring to the emergence of international political economy in the period after the World War II does not mean that similar conditions and developments that can be examined in the framework of the international

political economy did not occur before the World War II. Rather, it should be added that the scientific and research environment of the period after World War II also had more suitable conditions for the formation and development of this field of study (Harris and Garner, 2016). After the end of the war, a new wave of research was formed to theorize international relations, and as a result, the theoretical literature of international relations developed rapidly (Marable, 2015).

The formation of the interdisciplinary study area of international political economy was one of the results of this process. In the 1960s, international relations were influenced by the paradigm of behaviorism in social sciences, and after that, an attempt was made to provide a special classification of the specialized fields of this area. However, the program of separation and specialization of social sciences fields was gradually faced with theoretical and meta-theoretical challenges, and after that, the tendency to integrate and combine

fields became more prominent (Rujing, 2024). In this framework, international political economy is known as an interdisciplinary field of study that is one of the branches of international relations (Judd & Hinze, 2018: 36).

America's attempt to withdraw from the JCPOA nuclear agreement was a plan that Donald Trump had in mind since he participated in the US presidential election. Finally, the government of the United States of America officially announced its withdrawal from the JCPOA and the return of previous sanctions and declared its readiness to resume negotiations with Iran. In fact, confronting Iran and the policies of the Islamic Republic of Iran in the region has been one of the main topics of Trump's foreign policy (Estes, 2020: 19).

Trump has listed confronting Iran's military forces in the Persian Gulf and intensifying pressure on Iran in order to withdraw from regional policies as part of his main policies (Zhao, 2021). Before the implementation of the JCPOA, the Islamic Republic of Iran; The threat of terrorism is the threat of human rights and the nuclear threat, and after the nuclear agreement, the threat of the JCPOA, the basis of the threat of regional hegemony, and then the threat of missiles were built, and this chain will continue (Lokot & Bhatia, 2020).

After the withdrawal of the United States from the JCPOA, this country is trying to threaten Iran's economic interests by bringing in a significant number of international players and business partners, sometimes forcibly, and in fact involve Iran in some kind of repeated or consecutive sanctions game (Reinsberg et al., 2019). According to it, the target country either surrenders and changes its behavior or resists the demands of the sanctioning country. By resisting the imposed sanctions, the Islamic Republic has always refused to start negotiations and sign a new agreement by accusing the United States of violating international agreements and treaties (Schwartz & Scott, 2022: 61-62).

It should be noted that the Islamic Republic of Iran has been under sanctions by the United States and its allies almost since its inception, and therefore relatively many sources have been written in this field. The issue of UN sanctions and the EU oil embargo, etc., have been among the most important issues that have been addressed by researchers. But what distinguishes the current research from other researchers conducted in this field lies in the fact that with Trump taking office and announcing the policy of removing Iran from the global energy equation and the complete embargo on Iran's oil, many researchers in this field have only studied the announced dimensions of this policy and the effect of this policy on the pricing of energy sources and finally, they have analyzed its effectiveness or lack of effectiveness on the behavior of the Islamic Republic of Iran. Now, the current research intends to examine the aforementioned policy by examining its consequences in the field of political economy and energy, which is completely beneficial and efficient for the United States. In other words, the current research intends to focus on the nature of the

policy of removing Iran from the world's energy equations beyond the causal analysis of the aforementioned strategy and policy and whether it is successful or not. In this regard, the aim of this research was to compare the approaches of the macroeconomic strategy of the international political economy of the United States of America and China towards the Islamic Republic of Iran.

American political economy

The largest economy in the world is owned by the United States of America. This country ranks first in terms of nominal GDP and second in terms of GDP (Purchasing Power Parity or PPP) in the world (World Economic Outlook Database, 2024). The US dollar is the most commonly traded currency in the world and the American economy has grown significantly in recent decades due to its rich natural resources, large factories and domestic production, and industries such as computers, pharmaceuticals, space and military equipment (Goodfriend & McDermott, 2021). Of course, during the presidency of George Bush, the housing market experienced a bubble phenomenon, which led to a severe economic crisis on Wall Street (Birkinbine, 2020). The crisis lasted from 2007 to 2009 until the White House and Congress passed the Reinvestment Recovery Act, which injected liquidity into the market (Harris and Garner, 2016).

USA's main trading partners are China, Canada, Mexico, Japan, Germany, South Korea, England, France, India and Taiwan. The federal government of the United States of America is a republican government that includes the states of the United States with the capital Washington DC. is a district and territory of the United States of America. The federal government consists of three branches: Legislature, Executive and Judiciary. The US Constitution has assigned these powers to the US Congress, the US President, and the federal courts (such as the US Supreme Court), respectively (Josifidis & Supic, 2020). According to the constitution, there is a division of labor between the federal government and the state governments. Each state is autonomous in internal affairs and has the authority to form a local government, regulate internal trade relations, hold elections, deal with health and social welfare, and should only be under the command of the government in foreign affairs, the army, minting coins, printing banknotes and declaring war, etc. (Scott, 2024). The joint powers of the federal government and the states are to make laws, borrow money, establish courts, establish banks, provide public services, and pay social welfare costs. In general, it can be said that cultural, social and economic issues are within the jurisdiction of the state government and major decisions are the responsibility of the federal government (Goodfriend & McDermott, 2021).

China political economy

China's economy has changed rapidly since the late 1970s and is growing. Based on purchasing power parity, China has the world's second largest economy and a major player in the global economy (World

Economic Outlook Database, 2024). If China's current economic growth continues, China is about to catch up with America, which is the world's largest economy, and must prepare itself to deal with the political and economic consequences of this issue.

China's main industries are very broad and include iron and steel products, coal, machinery, petroleum and petrochemicals, toys, shoes, and electronics. Rice, wheat, potato, corn, peanut, tea, millet, barley, flax, fish and pig are the main agricultural products. China's main exports are machinery, clothing, shoes, toys, mineral fuel, chemicals, and its imports are machinery, chemicals, iron and steel and mineral fuel (Anderson et al., 2024).

The World Bank has described China's economic situation as favorable and the country's macroeconomic environment as stable but despite the increase in GDP, the per capita rate of economic output is still very low, and China still has a long way to go to reach the level of developed countries (Liu & Gao, 2024).

China is a strategic and geo-economic country due to the following components:

- Large population and size of the country
- Creation of about 2,000 free trade zones with special rules for those zones and ports equipped for loading with maximum capacity (Mearsheimer, 2021).
- Positioning between two strategic and geo-economics countries, Russia in the north and India in the south (Myers & Wise, 2016)
- Located between the Pacific Ocean and the Indian Ocean.
- Membership in important international and regional organizations such as SAARC and Shanghai and directly influencing these organizations (Liu & Lim, 2019).
- Access to the open waters of the world through the China Sea (Mearsheimer, 2021).
- Neighborhood with one of the economic powers and poles of the world, Japan (Myers & Wise, 2016).

China has taken pragmatic policies to maintain stability in the region, gain more economic benefits and increase political influence, without compromising on vital interests, and all of these are aimed at "continuing economic development and political stability" (Liu & Lim, 2019).

With the end of the Cold War and the change in the global polarization of power, China played a more active role in the international arena, which was the beginning of a new phase of its diplomacy. This issue reached its peak when Xi Jinping came to power as a symbol of the fifth generation of Chinese leaders who undertook an active foreign policy with a new detailed goal (Van Aaken & Kurtz, 2019). He followed his vision according to the model of the Chinese dream, which included the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation, with the aim of restoring ideological legitimacy and increasing global self-confidence in the Silk Road strategy. The Belt and Road Initiative and the Chinese Dream are placed in parallel in the field of China's domestic policy and foreign policy, and it implies

economic prosperity, national reconstruction, people's happiness and social harmony (Britton-Purdy et al., 2019).

China in this initiative by creating a community of common destiny, applying friendly policies and improving poor areas and increasing political and economic relations in the form of win-win cooperation while increasing allies, it pursues a safe internal and external environment with stability to maintain the interests and legitimacy of its political system in order to strengthen soft power (Kingstone, 2018: 67).

Political economy of Iran

Iran's economy is a mixed economy, including a large public sector, about 60% of which is managed in a centralized and command manner. A major part of Iran's exports is based on oil and gas exports (World Bank Report, 2022). From the point of view of economic equality, Iran's economy was adjusted after the Iran-Iraq war in such a way that it led to the formation of governmental economic experts and the paralysis of the people, especially the educated youth. According to the common opinion among economists, the economic opportunities in Iran are not equal for all its people, and many have reported the "paralysis" of the economy of the weak and young Iranian strata, and the inefficiency of the economy and insufficient domestic and foreign investment have increased inflation in the past years (Soofi & Hosseini, 2020).

In terms of GDP based on purchasing power parity, Iran is the 22nd largest economy in the world and based on nominal GDP based on the World Bank list, Iran's economy ranks 50th among countries in the world, but in proportion to the population, or the amount of GDP Per capita, which is one of the main measures of development, in 2020, Iran is ranked 156th in the world among 213 countries surveyed by the World Bank, with a per capita income of 2,422 US dollars (World Bank Report, 2022).

Iran's gross domestic product decreased by 160 billion US dollars during the 3-year period of the tightening of Western sanctions (2011-2014) and Iran dropped 7 places in the ranking of the world's major economies during this period. Based on this, Iran's GDP fell by 28% during the three-year period from 2011 to 2014 (Mossalanejad & Ahmadi Moien, 2017). Iran, which was ranked 21st among the world's largest economies in 2011, has dropped to 28th in 2014. Before the tightening of sanctions, i.e. in 2011, Iran's gross domestic product was estimated at 576 billion US dollars, but with the tightening of sanctions, this figure decreased to 557 billion dollars in 2012 (Hashemi et al., 2022).

The downward trend of Iran's GDP continued in 2013 and 2014, and Iran's GDP reached 493 billion dollars and 415 billion dollars in these years, respectively (Moameni et al., 2022). The report of the World Bank in June 2019 (June 2019) has predicted a negative 4.5% economic growth in Iran. While in January 2019, negative 3.6 was predicted. Also, Iran's GDP in 2019 has decreased by 8.7% compared to 2018. According to the assessment of the World Bank, in 2020 Iran's

economic growth was zero percent (World Bank Report, 2022) and this trend has not improved much.

China's policy towards Iran

The scope of cooperation between Iran and China was extended not only in the economic dimensions but also in the political-security field. In connection with the direction of political-strategic relations between the two countries, America has played a central role as a powerful actor in the international arena.

China implemented a dual policy by adopting a cautious stance towards Iran's nuclear program. On the one hand, China voted for sanctions resolutions against Iran's nuclear activities in the Security Council in the form of cooperation with the United States, and on the other hand, by adjusting some of their provisions, it tried to reduce the intensity of pressure on Iran and maintain friendly relations with this country (Guo et al., 2021). The reason for this can be found in the fact that the issued resolutions should not create a disturbance to the common interests of the two countries in the field of energy. In fact, the adoption of the approach of looking to the east was noticed by Iranian policymakers when they were looking for a kind of balance against their hegemonic domination with increasing pressure from Western countries (Van Aaken & Kurtz, 2019). This approach is somehow considered important in facilitating strategic cooperation between the two countries. In the framework of its initiative, China is looking for some kind of change in economic and strategic-security policies to increase its economic growth rate. Having strategic capabilities and being an important and influential actor in regional and extra-regional security arrangements, Iran can respond to China's strategic and defense-security needs in the Belt and Road Initiative (Guriev & Papaioannou, 2022). In terms of security, China and Iran are opposed to the American defense strategy in the areas under their influence.

One of the most important goals of China is to become a great power in the world arena, and therefore, the path chosen by the Chinese leaders is economic progress and development. Because all the emerging powers use the income of Iran's economy to strengthen their military base. England and Holland did this in the 18th century and became a maritime power and were able to acquire colonies in distant lands. Later, the United States strengthened its military power by increasing its economic power, especially during the period between the two world wars, and emerged as the most stable superpower in the world. China, as an emerging power, can translate economic power into military and political power in the long run, and this is the factor that has caused the United States to worry (Liu & Gao, 2024).

In the path of its economic growth and development, China needs the oil and energy of the Persian Gulf region. Therefore, one of the main concerns of the Chinese is the security of energy supply, which itself requires stability in this region. Because in a world where the oil and gas markets are strongly influenced by each other and the rapid economic growth of the

new economic superpowers has added to the insecurity of the markets. Vital fuels such as oil have a special place in the economic policies of producing countries and are also of particular importance in the economic security strategies of energy consumers. In this way, access to energy resources has become an important issue for countries that have recently entered the Jirga of major energy consumers, such as China with significant economic growth. China, as a developing country with an economic growth rate of 9%, has high energy consumption and it is increasing day by day. As long as China's population growth and economic growth continue at the current rate, the country's energy consumption will also increase at a higher rate than the current rate (Van Aaken & Kurtz, 2019). For this reason, the reliable and continuous import of oil has become a serious issue in the foreign policy of this country.

Thus, the drive for access to oil supply and the vulnerability to the need for increasing volumes of oil are important strategic interests that independently shape China's foreign policy. How China is perceived and its actual behavior will be highly related to domestic and international energy policies. Therefore, at the beginning of the 21st century, energy security is at the center of Beijing's intentions towards the Middle East and the Persian Gulf. Considering that the Middle East and the Persian Gulf are in the center of international energy, in 2004, China imported about 54% of its oil consumption from this region (Guriev & Papaioannou, 2022). The forecast of China's energy shortage is growing rapidly, and the International Energy Agency estimates that by 2030, China will need to import 75% of its energy (Guo et al., 2021). Chinese analysts believe that industrialized countries in previous periods also had limitations to ensure access to energy, and energy shortage is a problem that can disrupt China's rapid economic development (Mearsheimer, 2021).

Therefore, what China needs is stability and security in its oil interests and in the region itself. On the other hand, this country is trying to expand its influence in the region, but in the meantime, it is facing obstacles from a country like the United States of America. In this way, America is considered the most important competitor for this country, which can create many challenges for this country. Therefore, politically, by using oil diplomacy, the Chinese are seeking to increase the security factor of their imported oil through the intensification of diplomatic activities in the region. They believe that strong bilateral ties can increase the security of their oil supply, especially in times of crisis (Liu & Lim, 2019). In fact, the main issue that bothers the Chinese is that they have to import the oil they need from a region where America is the dominant player. Evidently, America's dominance is not limited to this region, but the energy field as a whole is also under the control of American, European and Japanese companies (Anderson et al., 2024).

China has implicitly accepted the role of the United States in the Middle East and especially in the Persian Gulf region, and has not made any obvious efforts to compete strategically with the United States in this region. China's positions on the US attack on Iraq and its positive vote on the Security Council resolutions against Iran are proof of this claim. Although China has accepted the role of the United States in this region, it has been against the hegemonic position of the United States and has expressed these oppositions in the form of some support for Iran and different positions from the United States in the United Nations Security Council (Liu & Lim, 2019). Therefore, the goal of China's strategy in the Middle East is to be present at the lowest level of balance of power, which does not mean confronting the United States, but to prepare for possible events. Finally, the goal of China in its foreign policy in the Persian Gulf region is not conflict but to avoid conflict.

The Chinese are well aware that maintaining the process of economic growth and development and, as a result, raising the level of well-being and as a result the political and economic stability of their country, import oil and especially ensuring the stability of its supply is of vital value to China. On the other hand, the Chinese realized that energy security can also be an area of strategic vulnerability for that country. As a result, the strategy of diversifying oil resources has been prioritized in this country. In this direction, China invests in all countries that have significant oil reserves. China's state-owned oil companies have made extensive investments in the Middle East, Central Asia and the Caucasus, Africa and to some extent in Latin America. Therefore, China is pursuing a supply diversification policy, under which Africa and Eurasia will remain as strategic oil suppliers. Nevertheless, practical obstacles have prevented a serious increase in China's imports from these two regions. For example, China's efforts to expand the energy alliance with Russia and some other Central Asian countries have faced problems due to the mistrust caused by past relations, the completely political nature of energy-related issues in these countries, and the rise of nationalism. In Africa, although China's efforts to attract attention through material aid have made good progress in countries such as Angola, Nigeria and Sudan, however, due to the lack of political and social stability and weak infrastructure in these countries, not much success has been achieved (Wang et al., 2024). Therefore, while Africa provides about 32% and Eurasia the remaining 20% of China's consumption needs, these regions are not comparable to the Middle East and the Persian Gulf in terms of the amount or life of the reserves, because, the oil of African countries cannot be compared with the oil of Middle Eastern countries. The total oil of important African countries, including Libya, Algeria, Nigeria, Angola and Egypt, is approximately 112 billion barrels, which is less than Iraq's oil. At the same time, the lack of stability and inappropriate infrastructure of African countries, along

with the great geographical distance, reduces the advantages of these countries' oil (Van Aaken & Kurtz, 2021).

Although the Chinese have made extensive efforts to invest in the discovery and extraction of energy resources in different parts of the world, but despite their great efforts to diversify their oil resources, the Persian Gulf is still considered the most important source of energy for China. Thus, China's interest in Persian Gulf energy resources shows a big gap between its energy needs and the ability to meet these needs. In such a situation, China cannot be indifferent to the issues of this region, but this country is cautiously planning to achieve a balance between geopolitical interests and energy economy in the Persian Gulf, because, China seeks to avoid any political friction with the United States of America (Zhou et al., 2024).

At present, the Chinese elites believe that the need to promote dignity based on the economic component of power is not confrontation but interaction. Although, China is not unwilling to be recognized as an actor balancing the power of America in the international system, but they know that this importance is not achievable in the near future (Wang et al., 2024). Therefore, China's current policy is to accept the leadership of the United States. In other words, although China cannot abandon the energy resources of the Persian Gulf region, it is inevitable to somehow associate itself with the policies of the United States of America in the region in order to ensure energy security in this region which is under the influence and control of the United States.

American policy towards Iran

The United States of America, with less than five percent of the world's population, is the largest consumer of energy, especially oil, in the world. With less than 3% of the world's oil reserves, this country consumes 20% of the world's produced oil (Josifidis & Supic, 2020). Therefore, the international economic policy of this country depends on this issue.

In the field of oil supplying areas, the Persian Gulf, having energy resources on the one hand and a special geopolitical and geostrategic position on the other hand, is considered to be an negligible area of interest for great powers such as the United States. The Middle East and the Persian Gulf, with 60% of the world proven oil reserves and 41% of the proven natural gas reserves, is the densest region in the world in terms of fossil fuel reserves, which can continue to play an active role in the economic competition of the great powers. Thus, the amount of American imports from the Persian Gulf region has increased during different periods (Goodfriend & McDermott, 2021).

In the 2014 BP Energy Outlook Report, North America's energy demand will grow at an average of 0.2% per year between 2012 and 2035 (World Economic Outlook Database, 2024). Therefore, it is obvious that major powers and even regional powers and secondary powers in the Gulf should pay attention to the oil and gas resources of the Persian Gulf. On the

other hand, the strong dependence on oil in this region can potentially bring costly requirements for the freedom of action of this country in the field of international relations and over time reduce the strength and power of this country. For this reason, in the energy strategy of the American presidents, especially in the strategy of Clinton and George Bush, a special emphasis was placed on reducing dependence on Persian Gulf oil. Therefore, following the outbreak of the fourth Arab-Israeli war in 1973 and the oil embargo of Western countries by the Arabs, an important plan called the independence project was presented by Richard Nixon, the president of the United States at the time, based on which, self-sufficiency by efforts in three areas of resource diversification fuel and imported, turning to new energies and efforts to optimize fuel consumption are focused (Lau et al., 2023). The goal of this project was to try to exploit domestic resources and thus achieve independence in the field of energy until the end of the 1980s, but the importance of the energy issue caused this plan to be on the agenda of all American governments from Nixon to Obama (Josifidis & Supic, 2020). Accordingly, compared to China, the Americans have sought to reduce their dependence on the Middle East region and the Persian Gulf.

By adopting a strategy of self-sufficiency in energy, USA seeks to reduce its dependence on this region and even achieve independence. In other words, the Americans are well aware that without serious action in the field of energy and considering the unstable political nature of the Middle East, along with the importance of this region in the world's energy supply, they have no choice but to pursue new policies in the field of energy. These policies should provide and guarantee the transfer of cheap oil from the Persian Gulf, something that has been in the strategy of all American presidents. In line with this plan, America's dependence on imported oil has decreased rapidly in recent years due to the increase in production and decrease in domestic consumption (Josifidis & Supic, 2020).

The most important issue in the current Biden government in 2023 is to increase or maintain the economic growth rate, increase employment and reduce inflation below 5%. In the two years of Biden's presidency, through bipartisan bills, the US government has succeeded in dealing with China, the environmental challenge, investing in renewable energy, managing Corona, assisting medium-sized entrepreneurs, and significantly increasing oil and gas production. export and "adaptation" to the Ukraine crisis, follow the quiet, gradual and broad international multilateralism measures (Rujing, 2024).

Increasing pressure on China, Iraq, Turkey, the UAE and India, Washington has adopted a policy of digital pressure and tougher sanctions management as part of Plan B. Biden's team has both focus and discipline in foreign policy. Saudi Arabia and Israel are far more active towards Iran than America and Europe. It can be said that America's remote control method in

relation to Iran will continue for at least the next two years when the Biden government is in charge. The foundations of this method are: political isolation, preventing foreign investment, extensive virtual activity to show internal contradictions such as inefficiency, increasing inflation rate, civil restrictions and meritocracy restrictions, and subjecting the public to financial openings to the approval of the Ministry of Treasury (Scott, 2024).

The evidence shows that this current method of America is very similar to the assumptions and strategy of America towards communism and the Soviet Union during the Cold War, which was designed by the American Russologist George Kennan. He believed that there is no need for military action to confront the Soviet Union. The Soviet Union is a self-destructive system and by designing a political strategy to block penetration and intensify its internal contradictions, it will lead to the implosion of the system over time. From his point of view, America does not need to initiate actions against the Soviet Union directly, but to do comparative and propaganda work around one issue and only the inefficiency of that system.

CONCLUSION

In this research, the approaches of the macroeconomic strategy of the international political economy of the United States of America and China were compared to the Islamic Republic of Iran. US-China relations are the most important and at the same time the most complicated relations in Asia. Due to the rapid growth of China and the efforts of the United States of America to maintain its power in the region, the two countries are in an increasing struggle to gain more power and influence in Asia and experience different levels of interaction and competition against each other. Washington is worried about the unpredictable consequences of competition with China, which may lead to a military conflict between the two countries; It has tried to put a range of containment strategies (positive to negative) in accordance with this country's assessment of the impact of China's rise on American hegemony, in order to restrain China and avoid direct confrontation with this country. The findings of the research showed that the United States has used a variety of strategies in an intelligent manner in dealing with its competitors in accordance with the geopolitical conditions of the region and the international public space. The United States of America as the only remaining great power from the era after the Second World War and the Cold War; It has always tried to establish its hegemony in the world and force others to submit and accept its desired order. Therefore, economic growth and development and control of the world's energy resources, especially the resources available in the Persian Gulf region, are considered essential for the stabilization and maintenance of this country's hegemony in the world. On the other hand, considering that this arena can be such that in case of insecurity in this region, the

hegemony of this country will be challenged. Therefore, for several decades, this country has focused its strategy on reducing dependence on energy imports. China is also one of the great powers that is trying to improve its position in the world arena, and this in turn determines the country's dependence on the energy resources of the Persian Gulf. Thus, what is important for China is the security of energy supply

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